

SUBNATIONAL PUBLIC FINANCE AND FISCAL SUSTAINABILITY: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIAN STATES

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Abstract

The fiscal policy of the Nigerian government has proven unsustainable due to income deficiencies and heightened government expenditure, leading to substantial budget deficits. This study analyzed the effect of subnational public finance components on the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria from 2016 to 2022. Panel data were sourced from state audited financial statements, the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, the National Bureau of Statistics, and the Ministry of Finance. Panel regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The study found that statutory allocation significantly affected the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria. The study also found that capital expenditure significantly affects fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. The study witnessed that recurrent expenditure has a negative significant effect on states' fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. Finally, the study concluded that public debt has an insignificant effect on states' fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. This reveals that public debt will not increase the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria. The study, therefore, recommends that state governments implement uniform fiscal policy measures to establish budget discipline, transparency, and accountability, with the objectives of improving living standards, increasing incomes, creating more jobs, enhancing education, and prioritizing the financing of local industries. Additionally, these measures should promote foreign investment by ensuring stable internally generated revenue, thereby aiding in the maintenance of fiscal sustainability.

Keywords: Public Internally Generated Revenue, Subnational Public Finance, Statutory Allocation, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Subnational fiscal sustainability is essential to remain stable and grow for federal states like Nigeria. The ability of Nigerian governments to sustain fiscal health and continue supplying key public services, such as education, healthcare, and infrastructure, is strongly dependent on their public finance components. The ability of states to efficiently manage resources and maintain long-term financial sustainability is directly impacted by these factors, including revenue generation, spending patterns, debt management, and fiscal transfers (Bahl & Bird, 2018).

State administrations in Nigeria are highly dependent on federal funding, which is mostly provided by oil earnings and is prone to changes in the price of oil globally as well as economic shocks. States are becoming more fiscally vulnerable due to their over-reliance on a single, erratic source of income, which raises questions about their capacity to maintain fiscal balance in times of economic depression (Adedokun, 2021). Additionally, poor tax administration, a lack of diversity in revenue sources, and inefficiencies in governance contribute to low internally generated revenue (IGR) in many states (Olaoye & Adekanbi, 2018). These difficulties make it more difficult to successfully manage their mounting debt loads and fund important development projects.

The low internal revenue mobilisation by subnational governments in Nigeria has been identified as a threat to fiscal sustainability (Adamu & Chandana, 2019). The Nigerian government's fiscal policy is unsustainable due to revenue shortfalls and increased government spending, resulting in huge budget deficits.

Abomaye and Usoro (2018) showed that Nigeria's revenue correlates with global movement in oil prices, as the oil sector remains the only mainstay of the Nigerian economy, providing about 80% of its revenue receipt and foreign earnings.

The NBS report indicates that the IGR for the 36 states and FCT was N612.87 billion in H1 2020, reflecting a year-on-year decline of -11.7% compared to N693.91 billion in 2019. In Q2 2020, the IGR for 36 states and the FCT was N259.73 billion, a decrease from N353.14 billion in Q1 2020, reflecting a quarter-on-quarter decline of -26.5%.

Lagos State possesses the largest Internally Generated Revenue, amounting to N204.51 billion in H1 2020, succeeded by Rivers State with N64.59 billion however Jigawa State reported the lowest Internally Generated Revenue.

In the first quarter of 2021, the internally generated revenue was N398,259,343,434.98, and in the second quarter, it reached N450,864,040,568.57, reflecting a growth of 13.21%. Lagos state has the highest Internally Generated Revenue with N267,232,774,434.06 in H1 2021, followed by FCT with N69,072,879,664.43 and Rivers state with N57,324,672,372.42 (CBN, 2022).

How states manage their expenditures affects their capacity to maintain a sustainable budget. Compared to capital initiatives that promote long-term economic growth, several Nigerian states excessively emphasise ongoing expenses like salaries and administrative costs (Ariyo & Raheem, 2020). States are under more fiscal strain due to rising debt levels and a lack of fiscal discipline, which raises questions about the sustainability of debt and the possibility of fiscal crises (Ebi & Emmanuel, 2019).

Maintaining the financial stability of Nigerian states depends on understanding how subnational public finance components affect fiscal sustainability. The necessity to investigate how the main pillars of public finance—debt management, revenue generation, spending trends, and fiscal transfers—affect the fiscal sustainability of Nigerian states serves as the driving force behind this study. Policymakers looking to strengthen economic resilience, lessen reliance on federal funding, and improve state-level fiscal governance will find great value in the study's conclusions (Ekpo, 2014).

The study also seeks to add to the body of knowledge on fiscal federalism and public finance by studying the relationship between state-level fiscal policies and their wider economic effects. To support long-term economic growth and development, it will also offer evidence-based suggestions on how Nigerian states may fortify their financial management systems, enhance revenue production, and implement sustainable fiscal policies (Fossati, 2020).

Research Hypotheses

From the structure of the problem, the following null hypotheses were formulated:

- H₀₁:** Subnational IGR revenue has no significant effect on the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** Subnational statutory allocation does not significantly affect the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria.
- H₀₃:** Subnational capital expenditure does not significantly affect the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria.
- H₀₄:** Subnational recurrent expenditure does not significantly affect the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria.
- H₀₅:** Subnational public debt does not significantly affect the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Subnational Public Finance Components

Subnational public finance pertains to the involvement of state governments in the economy, evaluating government revenue and expenditure of public authorities, and the modification of either to attain favorable outcomes and mitigate adverse impacts. It manages public funds in a country's economy, including revenue, expenditures, and debt load through various government and quasi-government institutions (Adenugba & Ogechi, 2013). Subnational public finance is crucial for state governments to allocate resources towards public multisector economic objectives and development, healthcare, education services, low-income housing, and other public services.

According to World and Nkoro (2012), the principles of subnational public finance include openness and accountability, promoting an equitable society, sharing the burden of taxation fairly, promoting equitable development, sharing the benefits and burdens of the use of resources and public borrowing equitably between present and future generations, using public money prudently and responsibly, and responsible financial management and clear fiscal reporting.

Subnational Public Internally Generated Revenue

According to World and Nkoro (2012), internally generated revenue refers to the revenue generated by the state government from sources within its jurisdiction or operations. This revenue is not sourced from federal funding, allocations, or subsidies. In Nigeria, at the state and local government levels, Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) encompasses taxes, rates, fees, fines, and other levies imposed on individuals and enterprises within their authority. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) released statistics on Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) at the state level, revealing that the 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) amassed N1.89 trillion in IGR in 2021, reflecting a 22% increase from the preceding year. Lagos State

achieved the highest Internally Generated Revenue in the nation, totaling N267.2 billion in the first half of 2021. Experts suggest state governments can boost their IGR by leveraging technology, especially in tax collection (NBS, 2021).

Subnational Statutory Allocation

Subnational statutory allocation refers to the revenue support the federal government provides to each state. This allocation is occasionally determined by variables such as state population, availability of natural resources, and the necessity for infrastructural development within the state. Statutory allocation refers to the balance in the Federation account after deducting 13 percent of the revenue generated from natural resources, which is allocated as a first-line charge for distribution to the beneficiaries of the derivation funds. Statutory allocation to the states is based on the sharing of the federation account in which 56% goes to the federal government, 24% to the state government, and 20% to local government (Olaoye & Bankole, 2019).

Subnational statutory allocation refers to the funds allocated by the state government to different entities for the performance of statutory functions (Onuigbo & Eme, 2015). These allocations are dictated by statutory formulas set by legislation. In Nigeria, the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 and the Allocation of Revenue (Federation Account, etc.) Act No.1 1982 mandates that revenues generated by the federal government be deposited into the Federation Account and distributed monthly among the three tiers of government as delineated in the Revenue Act 1982. These allocations fund development projects and foster good governance and equitable development.

Subnational Capital Expenditure

Subnational capital expenditures refer to expenditures on capital projects such as infrastructure, including roads, airports, healthcare, education, telecommunications, and electricity generation. Capital expenditures refer to the expenditures of the government, which are investments (Ugochukwu & Oruta, 2021). Such expenditures increase the existing stock of wealth and or reduce existing liability. This covers the total government spending on infrastructural facilities such as building health facilities, construction of new roads, bridges, farm mechanisation, dams, schools, mining, provision of rural electrification and communication outfits to reduce the unemployment rate (Araga, 2016). This study defines subnational government capital expenditure as funds utilized by states to acquire or maintain fixed assets, including land, buildings, and equipment, for the benefit of citizens.

However, Usman (2011) asserted that capital expenditure is used when the market proves inefficient or its outcomes are socially unelectable. In support of this notion, Khan (2019) opined that Government capital expenditure is the amount of money a government spends each year on public goods and related activities to deal with market inefficiencies, such as stabilisation of the economy, maintain a strong national defense, provision of public goods, and to deal with specific needs of society such as redistribute income that a free market system will not or cannot address on its own.

Subnational Recurrent Expenditure

Ugochukwu and Oruta (2021) defined subnational recurrent expenditures as administrative expenses such as wages, salaries, interest on loans and maintenance. Recurrent expenditure encompasses expenditures on the pay and salaries of public service employees and the operational costs associated with the functioning of government departments. It also pertains to the segment of government expenditure that neither generates assets nor diminishes obligations. Examples include employees' salaries and wages, consumption expenditure on debts, and financial aid (Yildirim & Yildirim, 2017). Recurrent expenditure refers to the expenses incurred during the accounting year. It primarily comprises expenditures on wages, salaries, and benefits, acquisitions of goods and services, and the consumption of fixed capital (depreciation). The concept of recurrent expenditure is used to denote the expenses that the government incurs for its maintenance and also for the society and economy as a whole (Bhatia, 2004). It also means all payments other than for capital assets, including goods and services (wages and salaries, employer contributions), interest payments, and subsidies (Philip, 2014). It is typically associated with the expenditure incurred for the ongoing repair, restoration, and upkeep..

Fiscal Sustainability

Fiscal sustainability refers to the government's capacity to finance its budget effectively over the long term without incurring excessive public debt. A technical concept of fiscal sustainability is frequently derived from the government's intertemporal budget constraint (IBC). A sustainable budget process requires that the expected present discounted value of all future stock of debt converge to 0 (Trehan & Walsh, 1991).

Earlier studies on fiscal sustainability, such as Domar (1944), discussed the issue of fiscal sustainability in the context of a growing economy. Domar's notion of budgetary sustainability is called Domar's stability condition. He characterized fiscal sustainability as a stabilizing debt-to-GDP ratio or deficit-to-GDP ratio. Domar's theorem posits that a sustainable fiscal strategy necessitates that the growth rate of national output (n) surpasses the cost of government borrowing (r) or the growth rate of public debt in the absence of new borrowing. Nonetheless, if borrowing costs surpass the growth rates of national output, any deficit may result in an indefinitely unsustainable fiscal policy. Domar's approach is new in that it facilitates the calculation of the necessary primary surplus (PS) or deficit to stabilize the debt-to-national production ratio at a specific level, given a particular growth-interest rate difference. Andrey et al. (2021) believe that fiscal sustainability, which is the ability of governments to sustain their current fiscal policies in the long run, is largely linked to the concept of fiscal risks. The sustainability of public finances influences intergenerational equity and reflects principles applicable universally to all governments, irrespective of their current levels of borrowing. Taofeek Olusola (2014) stressed that fiscal sustainability describes the condition of fiscal policies, perhaps due to the persistent implementation of fiscal rules, the absence of political apathy, and the existence of an economy that is free from perpetual debt accumulation. Consequently, fiscal sustainability is regarded as a multi-faceted notion.

Theoretical Framework

Maynard Keynes proposed his economic theory in 1936. Keynesian economists assert that fiscal policy is an essential instrument for sustainability management, with the government's role being pivotal in upholding fiscal sustainability within the economy. This is achieved by regulating aggregate demand until the economy reaches budgetary sustainability. Consequently, an augmentation of governmental instruments elevates aggregate demand. A slight decrease in personal income tax (PIT) enhances disposable income, augmenting aggregate demand. Nonetheless, government expenditure constitutes a component of aggregate demand. Keynes (1934) emphasized the aggregate demand function to mitigate fiscal unsustainability. The Keynesian perspective on long-run aggregate supply differs. They contend that the economy may operate below full capacity over the long term. Keynesians contend that output may fall short of full capacity due to several factors, including downwardly rigid wages (inefficiencies in labor market clearing) and a negative multiplier effect. A decline in aggregate demand results in decreased income for individuals, leading to reduced expenditure and generating a detrimental ripple effect, exemplifying the paradox of thrift. Consequently, during a recession, individuals experience a decline in confidence and subsequently increase their savings. Reduced expenditure leads to a subsequent decline in demand (Onofrei et al., 2020).

Keynes asserts that, in the short term, economic growth driven by fiscal unsustainability is significantly affected by aggregate expenditure. This theory views the economy as inherently unstable and necessitates proactive government involvement via expenditure to attain fiscal sustainability. Bowden (1982) and Ojong and Hycenth (2013) state that Keynesian theory posits that our ability to understand what determines the level of spending will help us know what determines the level of employment, output production and income in the economy. The Keynesian hypothesis posits that public expenditure stimulates economic activity and heightens fiscal sustainability, enhancing family perceptions of wealth through government spending and promoting increased savings.

Empirical Review

Wayas et al. (2024a) examined the effect of subnational public expenditure on states' fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. Panel regression was used to analyse the hypothesis significant effect between subnational public expenditure and states' fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. The study found that capital expenditure has a significant effect on states' fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. The study also found that recurrent expenditure negatively affects states' fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. Similarly, Wayas et al. (2024b) examined the effect of subnational public finance components on states' fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. The panel data were collected and sourced from Audited Financial Statements of subnational, CBN statistical Bulletin, CBN Annual report and accounts, and other publications of 36 states. The study found that internally generated revenue significantly affects states' fiscal sustainability in Nigeria. The study also found that statutory allocation significantly affects states' fiscal sustainability.

Maulid et al. (2022) examined the causal relationships among tax revenue, state expenditure, inflation, and economic growth in Indonesia from 1973 to 2019 to offer policy recommendations to the Indonesian government. This nation was chosen due to its remarkable economic growth and its recovery from the Asian economic crisis. An outline of the policies produced during the research period is provided to elucidate the government's actions. Quantitative methods were employed using the Vector Error Correction Model and Granger causality test to conduct a comprehensive investigation.

The findings indicated a positive long-term bidirectional causation between tax revenues and state spending, as well as between tax revenues and economic growth. This signifies that the government's initiatives to execute state expenditure have augmented tax income. Conversely, an augmentation in tax revenue enables the government to allocate funds for state expenditures, encompassing development and various activities, so enhancing the populace's economy and fostering economic progress.

Nevertheless, test results indicate that inflation is a consequence of economic expansion, rather than the reverse. This variable adversely impacts tax revenue, state expenditure, and economic growth; therefore, it must be mitigated to ensure stable economic growth. In contrast, the majority of the in-text citations were not included in the references of the article.

Onofrei et al. (2021) emphasized the particularity of fiscal sustainability in certain developing EU nations by examining the effects of fiscal regulations on governmental fiscal conduct. We utilize a panel data analysis to assess developing EU nations from 2000 to 2014, examining the convergence of fiscal responsibility metrics by calculating the convergence score of fiscal responsibility. The research employs interdisciplinary coordinates to integrate assessments from legal and financial viewpoints, so enhancing the literature that explores the connection between the legal framework governing governmental decision-making and the sustainability of public financing.

The selection of the study sample pertaining to developing EU nations constitutes a significant contribution and a reference point for literature examining the sustainability of these countries, emphasizing the critical role of fiscal risk management and control mechanisms in improving public sector performance and fiscal sustainability. The findings indicate the necessity of strengthening the interplay between the legal and institutional frameworks by identifying best practices for designing and operating effective independent fiscal institutions, enabling them to advise the government on fiscal policy and advocate for prudent fiscal policy and sustainable public finance.

Udeh (2021) determined the impact of the government's non-oil revenue on Nigeria's fiscal sustainability. The research encompasses a duration of thirty-five years, spanning from 1981 to 2015. The research employed an ex-post facto design to fulfill its objectives. The researcher employed various linear regression models. Secondary statistics regarding oil and non-oil revenue of the government for the specified period were obtained from the CBN statistical bulletin. Economic growth, the dependent variable, was indicated by gross domestic product (GDP).

The researcher employed the augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test, co-integration test, and error correction model for data analysis. The data indicate that both oil and non-oil revenue have a positive and considerable impact on gross domestic product. Consequently, the study did not perform a post-estimation test.

Ilori and Akinwunmi (2020) analyzed the impact of non-oil revenue generation on Nigeria's fiscal sustainability and economic progress from 1989 to 2018, utilizing secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria's statistical bulletin. The research utilized the model for analytical co-integration and error correction. The research utilized the co-integration model and the error correction model. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was employed to assess the stationarity of the time series. Comparable analytical methodologies were utilized for the multivariate data concerning oil and non-oil revenue components, exchange rates, and real gross domestic products.

Findings revealed that oil revenue adversely affects real gross domestic product in Nigeria, similar to the impacts observed from non-oil revenue. Nevertheless, Nigeria's exchange rate indicates a favorable trend and demonstrates statistical significance concerning real gross domestic product. The study concludes that the persistent decline in global crude oil prices, insurgent resistance in Nigeria's oil-producing regions, the extravagant spending of the Nigerian Government, the global COVID-19 pandemic, and other factors are detrimental to Nigeria's economic development.

Falade (2020) analyzed the impact of fiscal policy factors on the performance of the primary economic sectors—Industrial, Agricultural, and Services—utilizing an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) and Error Correction Model (ECM) for the period from 1970 to 2018. The results suggested that neither domestic nor international debts significantly affect the three analyzed sectors in the short run; however, foreign debt and government consumption expenditure were found to have incremental effects on the output of the industrial sector. It was similarly noted that domestic debt enhances the outputs of the agricultural and services sectors, whereas it adversely affects industrial output in the long term.

It is significant to notice that government investment expenditure favorably influences industrial output, whereas its impact on agricultural output is adverse in the long term. This indicates that the government can mitigate the adverse impacts of its domestic debt on industrial output by either augmenting its consumption expenditure or increasing reliance on foreign debt. The government is advised to prioritize investments in infrastructure, including irrigation systems, access roads to agricultural land, storage facilities, and processing equipment such as milling machines, to enhance production in the industry.

Saibu (2018) analyzed public expenditure, fiscal sustainability, and macroeconomic performance in Nigeria. Employing the intertemporal budget constraint framework for the government, a fiscal sustainability equation is formulated, and the prerequisites for achieving sustainability are determined. The empirical technique employs the unit root test, cointegration test, and dynamic OLS (DOLS) regression method to assess the sustainability of the fiscal posture from 1961 to 2016.

The empirical evidence indicates weak sustainability, particularly as evidenced by the DOLS regression results. Likewise, the findings regarding the impact of fiscal sustainability on economic performance indicate a feeble correlation between the two variables. The findings of this study do not markedly differ from existing research in this area of literature.

The primary policy implication of this research is that the Nigerian government must establish a more robust and systematic connection between tax and expenditure policies and the progression of public debt. A emphasis on establishing a short-term governmental constraint framework and fiscal sustainability indicators to signal and rectify short- and medium-term budgetary imbalances will be a valuable avenue for future research.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed an ex post facto research design. Ex post facto design delineates the correlation between historical variables and current trends or events. The study's population comprises the public sector finances of the 36 states within the Nigerian subnational economy. The finances of the subnational public sector in the Nigerian economy consist of state government finances.

The research sample of this study is subnational. This is done after applying the purposive sampling technique (Kothari, 2004). This study examines how subnational government finances affect the Nigerian economy to draw inferences on the study population from the regression based on the Sample Regression Function (SRF) specified (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). This study's data pertains to the financial status of the state government from 2016 to 2022. The data are disseminated in both internal and external publications pertaining to federal and state government finances.

The internally published documents include Audited Financial Statements of subnational entities, the CBN Statistical Bulletin, the CBN Annual Report and Accounts, various CBN publications, publications from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and the Ministry of Finance (MOF) Medium Term Fiscal Framework along with additional publications. The external published materials include the World Bank's World Development Indicators, the UNDP Human Development Report, BudgiT, and publications from other international organizations.

The credibility and acknowledgment of both internal and external secondary sources (organizations) augment the reliability and appropriateness of the data acquired for this investigation. The panel data was analyzed with E-Views version 12. Descriptive statistics, a correlation matrix, a normality test, and regression analysis will be conducted, along with post-estimation analyses including a heteroskedasticity test, serial correlation assessment, and Hausman test.

The model outlined below for the Hausman test presents a practical variant for regression applications, which assesses whether certain transformations of the original regressors possess zero coefficients.

$$SUI_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SPIGR_{it} + \beta_2 SSA_{it} + \beta_3 SPCE_{it} + \beta_4 SRE_{it} + \beta_5 SPD_{it} + e_{it}$$

Where

SUI = Sustainability index

SPIGR= Subnational Public Internally Generated Revenue

SSA= Subnational Statutory Allocation

SPCE= Subnational Public Capital Expenditure

SRE= Subnational Recurrent Expenditure

SPD= Subnational Public Debt

e = Stochastic error term

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4,$ and β_5 are regression parameters

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	SUI	SPIGR	SSA	SRE	SPCE	SPD
Mean	0.482351	10.05605	10.31479	10.93187	8.586466	11.09165
Median	0.312811	10.16718	10.19987	10.89220	10.52937	11.07998
Maximum	1.951880	11.81940	11.65365	12.01590	11.78057	12.13664
Minimum	-0.187087	8.476896	9.605279	10.13119	0.591228	10.45941
Std. Dev.	0.448893	0.658910	0.465753	0.283688	3.999230	0.275503
Skewness	0.906195	-0.518080	0.464893	0.859909	-1.366023	0.729216
Kurtosis	2.829795	3.437027	2.552935	4.885579	2.925947	5.077030
Jarque-Bera	24.85294	9.484653	7.982770	48.84888	52.59814	48.30806
Probability	0.000004	0.008718	0.018474	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum Sq. Dev.	36.06932	77.71498	38.82972	14.40570	2686.965	13.58647
Observations	216	216	216	216	216	216

Source: E-Views 12 Output, 2024

Table 1 presented the data utilized in the study, indicating that the fiscal sustainability index has a mean value of 0.482351, signifying that, on average, the fiscal sustainability index for states in Nigeria is 0.482351. The standard deviation from the mean was 0.448893; the fiscal sustainability index had a normal distribution as the standard deviation was proximate to the mean. Similarly, it possesses a median of 0.312811, with skewness and kurtosis values of 0.906195 and 2.829795, respectively. The greatest sustainability index of states in Nigeria during the study period was 1.951880, indicating that the maximum index exceeded this value, while the lowest sustainability index recorded was -0.187087. The positive Jarque-Bera statistic of 24.85294 validates the normality of the data. Furthermore, the mean value of internally generated revenue is 10.05605, with a standard deviation of 0.658910. The mean of internally generated revenue had a normal distribution, since the standard deviation was less than the mean. Similarly, it exhibited a median of 10.16718, with skewness and kurtosis values

of 0.518080 and 3.437027, respectively. The peak internally generated revenue of states in Nigeria during the study period was 11.81940, indicating that the highest internally generated revenue did not exceed 11, while the lowest was approximately 8.476896. The positive Jarque-Bera statistic of 9.484653 validates the normality of the data. The statutory allocation has a mean of 10.31479, with a standard deviation of 0.465753. This indicates that the statutory allocation followed a normal distribution, as the standard deviation was less than the mean. Similarly, it exhibited a median of 10.19987, with skewness and kurtosis values of 0.464893 and 2.552935, respectively. The maximum statutory allocation of states in Nigeria during the study period was 11.65365, indicating that the highest allocation did not exceed 11.6, while the minimum allocation was approximately 9.605279. The Jarque-Bera statistic of 7.982770 validates the normality of the data.

Capital expenditure has a mean of 8.586466, with a standard deviation of 3.999230. This indicates that capital spending followed a normal distribution, as the standard deviation was less than the mean. Similarly, it exhibited a median of 10.52937, with skewness and kurtosis values of -1.366023 and 2.925947, respectively. The maximum capital expenditure of states in Nigeria during the study period was 11.78057, indicating that the highest capital expenditure did not exceed 11.7, while the minimum capital expenditure for the same period was roughly 0.591228. The Jacque-Bera statistic of 52.59814 validates the normality of the data.

The mean value of recurrent expenditure is 10.93187, with a standard deviation of 0.283688. This indicates that recurrent expenditure followed a normal distribution, as the standard deviation was less than the mean. Similarly, it exhibited a median of 10.89220, with skewness and kurtosis values of 0.859909 and 4.885579, respectively. The maximum recurrent expenditure of Nigerian states during the study period was 12.01590, indicating that the highest recurrent expenditure did not exceed 12.0, while the minimum recurrent expenditure for the same period was approximately 10.13119. The Jacque-Bera statistic of 48.84888 validates the normality of the data. The average public debt is 11.09165, with a standard deviation of 0.275503. This indicates that public debt followed a normal distribution, as the mean exceeded the standard deviation. Similarly, it exhibited a median of 11.07998, with skewness and kurtosis values of 0.729216 and 5.077030, respectively. The maximum public debt of Nigerian states throughout the study period was 12.13664, indicating that the highest public debt did not exceed 12.1, while the smallest public debt for the same period was about 10.45941. The Jarque-Bera statistic of 48.30806 validates the normality of the data.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	SUI	SPIGR	SSA	SRE	SPCE	SPD
SUI	1.0000	-0.7412	-0.3501	-0.1646	-0.8183	-0.13909
SPIGR	-0.74122	1.0000	0.7141	0.4022	0.8250	0.4649
SSA	-0.35018	0.7141	1.0000	0.2991	0.6781	0.4684
SRE	-0.16468	0.4022	0.2991	1.0000	0.0713	0.5038
SPCE	-0.81837	0.8250	0.6786	0.0713	1.0000	0.2202
SPD	-0.13909	0.4649	0.4684	0.5038	0.2202	1.0000

Source: E-Views Output (2024)

Table 2 elucidates the relationship between components of public finance and the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria, indicating that the fiscal sustainability index is connected with IGR at a value of -0.74, which denotes a lack of correlation due to the negative value. The fiscal sustainability index had a correlation of -0.35 with statutory allocation, indicating a lack of linkage due to the negative value. The fiscal sustainability index exhibited a correlation of -0.16 with recurrent expenditure, indicating a negative connection due to the low value. The fiscal sustainability index had a correlation of -0.81 with capital expenditure, indicating a low association due to the negative value. The fiscal sustainability index had a connection of -0.13 with public debt, indicating a low negative association.

Likewise, internally generated revenue had a correlation of -0.74 with the fiscal sustainability index, indicating a lack of linkage due to the negative value. The internally generated revenue exhibited a correlation with statutory allocation of 0.71, indicating a strong association as the value approaches 1.

Additionally, internally generated revenue had a correlation of 0.40 with recurrent spending, indicating a positive relationship due to the substantial value. The correlation between internally generated revenue and capital expenditure was 0.82, indicating a strong positive relationship. Ultimately, internally generated revenue had a correlation with public debt of 0.46, indicating a strong positive relationship.

The statutory allocation had a correlation of -0.16 with the fiscal sustainability index, indicating the absence of correlation due to the negative value. The statutory allotment had a correlation with IGR of 0.71, indicating a strong positive relationship. The statutory allotment had a correlation of 0.29 with recurrent spending, indicating a positive link due to the elevated amount. The correlation between statutory allocation and capital spending was 0.67, indicating a strong positive relationship. The statutory allocation exhibited a correlation of 0.46 with public debt, indicating a strong positive relationship.

Furthermore, recurrent expenditure exhibited a correlation of -0.16 with the fiscal sustainability index, indicating a lack of correlation due to the negative value. In contrast, recurrent expenditure demonstrated a correlation of 0.40 with IGR, signifying a strong correlation owing to the positive value. Furthermore, recurrent spending connected with statutory allotment of 0.299, indicating a positive link due to the elevated amount. Recurrent expenditure correlated with capital expenditure of 0.07, indicating a positive link. Ultimately, recurrent expenditure had a correlation with public debt of 0.50, indicating a positive relationship.

Capital expenditure exhibited a correlation of -0.81 with the fiscal sustainability index, indicating no correlation due to the negative value. Conversely, capital expenditure demonstrated a correlation of 0.82 with IGR, signifying a strong positive correlation. Furthermore, capital expenditure exhibited a correlation with the statutory allocation of 0.67, indicating a strong positive link due to the elevated value. Capital spending correlated with recurrent expenditure of 0.07, indicating a strong positive relationship. Ultimately, capital spending correlated with public debt of 0.22, indicating a favorable relationship.

Ultimately, public debt exhibited a correlation of -0.13 with the fiscal sustainability index, indicating a lack of linkage due to the negative value. Public debt correlated with IGR of 0.46, indicating a strong positive relationship.

Furthermore, public debt correlated with statutory allocation of 0.46, indicating a positive link due to the elevated value. Public debt correlated 0.50 with recurrent expenditure, indicating a strong positive relationship. Ultimately, public debt had a correlation with capital expenditure of 0.22, indicating a favorable relationship.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 3: Empirical results

Variable	Coefficient	t-statistics
C	-0.694561	-0.651435
SPIGR	0.167713	2.751917***
SSA	0.509660	9.706155***
SPCE	0.110652	12.12416***
SRE	-0.214511	-2.998450***
SPD	0.081975	0.739859
F-statistics	20.57998	0.000
Hausman test	25.903161	0.000
Serial correlation	11.75870	0.3015
Hetest	1.977529	0.1256
Stability test	2.295341	0.1365
R ²	0.865	
Adjusted R ²	0.823	

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

The Hausman test results in Table 3 demonstrate that the random effects regression model is the most suitable model for analyzing the study's data. The fixed effect was rejected with a probability of 0.0001. Consequently, the random effects estimator was employed to do the regression analysis. The study rejects the null hypothesis, which posited that internally generated revenue significantly affects states' fiscal sustainability in Nigeria at a 5% significance level, indicating that an increase in internally generated revenue correlates with enhanced fiscal sustainability for states in Nigeria. The findings suggest that IGR can facilitate the establishment of financial reserves during prosperous periods by allocating revenue surpluses into stabilization funds. Consequently, enhancements in domestically generated money from various sources can strengthen budgetary sustainability. Studies by Adamu and Chandana (2019) and Adenugba and Ogechi (2013) corroborate the conclusions of this research. The research by Nnanseh and Akpan (2013) and Aluthge et al. (2021) contradict the conclusions of this study.

Consequently, statutory allocation substantially influenced the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria at a 5% significance level, suggesting that an increase in statutory allocation will directly enhance the fiscal sustainability of these states. The findings suggest that statutorily allotted monies can substantially affect the financial health and viability of state government

organizations. Consequently, the statutory allocation of funds can significantly influence the budgetary viability of governmental institutions. Studies by Olaoye and Bankole (2019) and Igyo et al. (2016) corroborate the conclusions of this research. Nonetheless, the research conducted by Olaoye and Bankole (2019) contradicts the conclusions of the study.

The study rejects the null hypothesis, which posited that capital expenditure significantly affects the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria at a 5% significance level, indicating that an increase in capital expenditure correlates with enhanced fiscal sustainability for these states. The findings suggest that investment in infrastructure and social sectors is essential for long-term development and can affect a nation's fiscal sustainability. The precise effect of capital expenditure on the fiscal sustainability of Nigerian states necessitates a more focused examination of the nation's economic and financial conditions. The research conducted by Ugochukwu and Oruta (2021), as well as Abdulazeez (2021), corroborates the conclusions of this study. The research conducted by Yıldırım and Yıldırım (2017), Wandeda et al. (2021), and Ubesie (2016) contradict the conclusions of the study.

Furthermore, recurring expenditure exerted a statistically significant negative impact on the fiscal sustainability of Nigerian states at a 5% significance level, suggesting that an increase in recurrent expenditure will diminish the fiscal sustainability of these states. The findings suggest that substantial government expenditure on wages, salaries, and upkeep may adversely impact budgetary sustainability. Consequently, if recurrent expenditure is not meticulously handled, it may result in enduring financial imbalances, possibly jeopardizing a government's capacity to maintain its current expenditures and policies without endangering its solvency. The research conducted by Nurwanti et al. (2021), Aluthge et al. (2021), Chukwu, and Udochukwu (2019) corroborates the findings of this study. The research by Dahliah (2021) and Adamu and Chandana (2019) contradict the conclusions of this study.

Ultimately, public debt exerted a negligible influence on the fiscal sustainability of Nigerian states at a 5% significance level, suggesting that an escalation in public debt will not enhance the fiscal sustainability of these states. The findings suggest that Nigeria's substantial debt profile is deemed unsustainable, as the government is unable to fulfill its existing and forthcoming payment obligations. The research conducted by Itsede (2019), Okwu et al. (2016), Salau, and Obayelu (2017) corroborates the findings of this study. The studies conducted by Joshua (2015), Mohanty, and Panda (2019) contradict the conclusions of the research.

Post-Evaluation Outcome

The Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test demonstrates the absence of autocorrelation. The statistic of 11.75870 and its associated P-value of 0.30 are supported by the observed Pesaran scaled LM of the auxiliary regression, which has a P-value of 0.468.

Based on the heteroskedasticity test results in Table 3, it is essential to note that tests for heteroskedasticity were performed on the aggregated data to examine the potential for spurious regression among the variables (constant variance). The findings suggest that we accept the alternative hypothesis indicating the absence of constant variance among the analyzed firms,

demonstrating that the data is affected by heteroskedasticity. The stability signifies that the study is devoid of abnormal fluctuations, indicating that the data are normal. The statistics of 2.295341 and the associated P-value of 0.1365, which above 0.05, support this assertion. The Ramsey RESET omitted variable test presented in Table 3 indicated the existence of omitted variables, necessitating the implementation of conventional least squares regression procedures.

Figure 1: normality test

Figure 1 shows that since the probability is 0.0000 and the series has fulfilled the peritest required for the use of the regression model, the study will go ahead and generate various relevant Hausman Tests.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This study analyzed the effects of subnational public finance component on the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria over a seven-year period (2016 – 2022). The results indicated that locally generated revenue substantially influences the economic sustainability of states in Nigeria. Consequently, an augmentation in internally generated revenue will inherently enhance the budgetary sustainability of governments in Nigeria.

In summary, internally produced money is essential for the economic viability of Nigerian governments. By diversifying revenue sources and tackling difficulties, governments can establish new streams of reliable, sustainable income to finance services and promote economic growth.

The research indicated that statutory allocation substantially influenced the budgetary sustainability of governments in Nigeria. An augmentation in statutory allocation will consequently enhance the fiscal viability of governments in Nigeria. Consequently, it was determined that statutorily assigned monies can significantly influence the budgetary

sustainability of government. The research indicated that capital expenditure substantially influences budgetary sustainability in Nigeria.

An increase in capital expenditure will consequently enhance the budgetary sustainability of governments in Nigeria. Consequently, it was determined that capital expenditure substantially impacts the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria, directly affecting the nation's developmental results and long-term financial stability. The study observed that recurrent expenditure adversely impacts the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria. An increase in recurrent expenditure will diminish the fiscal viability of governments in Nigeria. Consequently, it was determined that recurrent expenditure could adversely impact the fiscal sustainability of governments, particularly if it is misaligned with long-term income generation and economic growth.

The study ultimately determined that public debt exerts a minimal influence on the fiscal sustainability of states in Nigeria. This indicates that public debt will not enhance the fiscal sustainability of governments in Nigeria.

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the further recommendations are as follows:

- i. The state governments should adopt consistent fiscal policy measures that can entrench budget discipline, transparency, and accountability aimed at raising levels of living, higher incomes, the provision of more jobs, better education, and greater attention to financing of local industries, also to enhance foreign investment by ensuring steady internal generated revenue which will help to control the level of fiscal sustainability.
- ii. Government should increase the statutory allocation-sharing formula in favor of the state government because many states are unable to finance their expenditure. Hence the viability of many states and the need to allocate more resources and power to the lower-tier governments to enhance their fiscal capability and operational efficiency.
- iii. The state governments of Nigeria should adhere strictly to the implementation of capital expenditure to increase the level of infrastructural and productive base in Nigeria which will have the capacity to stimulate economic growth and create employment.

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